

ISSUES OF INCREASING COGNITIVE ACTIVITY OF PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN THE COURSE OF THE LESSON

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ABSTRACT

This article covers the ways of improving the education and education of Primary School students of primary school teachers, issues of formation of cognitive activity of students, results of cognitive activity of students, methods of development of cognitive activity, various tasks of interactive didactic materials.

Keywords: personality, cognitive activity, communication, education, knowledge actualization, electronic simulators, interactive materials, crossword.

ВОПРОСЫ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ ПОЗНАВАТЕЛЬНОЙ АКТИВНОСТИ МЛАДШИХ ШКОЛЬНИКОВ В ПРОЦЕССЕ УРОКА

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АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье освещаются пути совершенствования обучения и воспитания младших школьников учителями начальных классов, вопросы формирования познавательной активности учащихся, результаты познавательной деятельности учащихся, методы развития познавательной активности, различные задачи интерактивного дидактического материала.

Ключевые слова: личность, познавательная деятельность, общение, обучение, актуализация знаний, электронные тренажеры, интерактивные материалы, кроссворды.

In recent years, there has been an increase in the activism of primary school teachers in seeking better ways to educate and educate primary school students. This can be reflected in the change in the direction of the educational process, when it is directed to create conditions for the development of the personality of each child. Personality development, on the other hand, requires certain conditions and actions. The new standards of education offer conditions that distinguish openness, multilevel,

flexibility and where the student chooses his educational path and the way to adapt to the school.

It is known that children learn effectively if they have the opportunity to follow their interests, make choices and actively communicate with each other. We want to develop the desire and love of reading in children, critical thinking, to educate creative and socially responsible individuals through active education that encourages students to use different forms of learning. If each teacher sees himself as a reformer of his daily experience, the most sustainable educational reform will be successful.

Thus, the child is a person who acts actively and consciously, and not as a blind performer of the teacher's will, being a "subject of educational activity", effectively applies interactive teaching methods that allow you to stimulate motivation and interest in the field of studied subjects and in the general education plan; helps to increase the level of activity and independence of students, Activity and dialogical interaction with the teacher and other participants in the educational process; the development of analysis, critical thinking, interaction, communication skills is considered important.

The formation of cognitive activity of students is one of the pressing problems of the entire educational process. In the process of developing cognitive activity, three groups of stages of knowledge acquisition can be distinguished:

1. Beginner (actualization of supportive knowledge, motivation and goal setting, perception and understanding);
2. Medium (consolidation and application);
3. Final (generalization and systematization).

Obviously, cognitive activity performs the role of an important psychological neoplasm, which should develop at all stages of teaching a child at school. But the age of Primary School is considered the priority age for the formation of mental and cognitive abilities, since during this period the study in the child comes first. Cognitive interest has a huge stimulating force: it forces you to actively strive for knowledge, actively seek ways and means to satisfy your thirst for knowledge.

The activities of the student are carried out in different directions, so it is important that these processes are controlled by adults. Only in this case can good results be achieved in the development of the personality of the reader. With the help of experienced mentors, the activity inherent in a child of a young age can become an effective activity. L. V. Zankov argued that in the system he created, "the activity of schoolchildren in education ensures the development of their creative capabilities, new cognitive needs and cognitive activity skills" [3].

But at the same time, it is necessary to take into account the individual characteristics of the personality of the reader. Depending on the situation, cognitive

activity is carried out in different forms. And here it is very important that the teacher recognizes these manifestations in the child. G. I. There is the following classification of intellectual activity used by Shchukin (Figure 1):

Figure 1. Classification of intellectual activity

The next sign is the emotional attitude expressed in response to the educational reality that is, voluntary manifestations:

- stability of attention (low level of distraction);
- the behavior of the student in difficult situations (as a rule, students are looking for different approaches to solving problem situations);
- completeness of actions (indicator-reaction to external stimuli (call from the lesson) to satisfy the emotional state, and not the requirements of the educational process [3].

Workbooks with individual electronic simulators fully meet the requirements of the standards of the second generation and allow you to form a positive attitude of students to learning, giving each child the opportunity to choose an individual educational speed.

Interactive didactic materials include various tasks:

- trials;
- logical tasks for setting compatibility or patterns;
- to restore text;
- by definition of "excess understanding";
- development of game tasks such as crosswords and crosswords.

The reader's task is to read the question, analyze the proposed answer options, choose the right one from their point of view and confirm their choice, and then proceed to the next question through the pointer at the bottom right of the screen. There is also information on how many questions are on the test and what question the reader is currently working with.

After all the answers are given, it is recommended to give the "result" command, and statistics for performing the test appear on the screen i.e.: how many correct answers, how many wrong and how many questions are not given at all.

As a conclusion, it can be said that the condition for constructive communication is respect for the interlocutor. The ability to listen and hear him, ask questions and express your opinion, find evidence and use them reliably. All this provides interactive teaching methods and saves the educator's labor in the lesson in achieving the lesson effective.

The level of formation of cognitive activity was determined, work was carried out on the use of interactive methods of teaching in classes to increase cognitive activity, an increase in the dynamics of the level of cognitive activity of their students was observed.

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